

Data Management Plan (DMP) for the Top Citizen Science Project SUNRISE

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DMP Version	Effective Date	Changes
SUNRISE_ Eglseer_1.0 Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11066249	25.04.2024	Initial version sent to FWF

General information	
Project Coordinator and Principal Investigator/ data officer responsible for data management and DMP	Dr. Doris Eglseer, MSc, BBSoc; Institute of Nursing Science, Medical University of Graz, orcid.org/0000-0002-9739-7555
Project title and acronym	SUstainable healthy NutRition In nurSing homEs (SUNRISE)
Project abstract	<p>The overall objective of the SUNRISE project is to collaboratively develop a feasible guideline for implementing sustainable healthy nutrition in nursing homes by using a Citizen Science approach. The specific aims are (1) to identify situations, conditions, and aspects that hinder or support sustainable healthy nutrition in nursing homes, (2) to explore individual experiences with and individual perspectives on sustainable healthy nutrition in the everyday lives of residents and staff, (3) to evaluate the perceptions of residents and staff with regard to the environmental benefits of the WHO's official recommendations on sustainable healthy nutrition 12 and to evaluate their readiness to adopt these behaviours in the nursing home setting, and (4) to iteratively combine, discuss, and interpret the collected data to collaboratively create a comprehensive and feasible guideline for sustainable healthy nutrition in nursing homes.</p> <p>Approach: In this project we will use photovoice, qualitative interviews, a survey, and ThinkCamps to collect and analyse data. Nursing home staff and residents will be our Citizen Scientists (CSs) and involved in different stages of the research process. Photovoice will be done by the CSs, which will take photographs, build coding frames, and discuss and interpret results in so-called ThinkCamps in collaboration with research team members. The second method will require the CSs to interview each other. They will be involved in collecting, discussing, and interpreting the gathered data in the ThinkCamps. For the planned survey, CSs are involved in the data analysis and interpretation. The results obtained from applying these first three methods will be interpreted and discussed by CSs and the research team members collaboratively in planned ThinkCamps.</p>
Start and end date of project	01.06.2024-31.05.2026
Funding programme/ grant number	FWF Top Citizen Science 142
Medical University of Graz project management ID/ Medical University of Graz project notification ID	13154/ 7929
Relevant policies and guidelines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical University of Graz "Policy für Forschungsdatenmanagement" • Medical UNIVERSITY of Graz "Standards of Good Scientific Practice"

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Medical University of Graz “Open Access Policy” • Medical University of Graz “Guidelines for Data Protection and IT Security” • FWF “Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities” • FWF “Core Requirements for Data Management Plans from Science Europe”
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I	Data Characteristics
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I.1	Description of the data	<p>Data type, format, and volume</p> <p>We will use photos, interviews and questionnaires to generate quantitative and qualitative data (in detail see table below). We plan to involve 10 citizen scientists (residents and nursing home staff) from one nursing home.</p> <p>Preparation of the qualitative data: A professional company will transcribe all interviews. Transferring data to/from the company will be performed after pseudonymizing the interviews by using the ACOnet file sender of the Medical University of Graz in accordance with the data protection rules. At the end of the project, all files are stored in formats that are as open and standardized as possible. The file format PDFA, and CSV as well as rtf are used for this purpose. Where conversion to an open format is not possible, original formats are stored.</p>
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Quantitative Data									
Investigation	Data Source	Method	Measurement instrument	Data type	Data file format		Processing software	File location	Estimated data volume
					Raw	Analyzed			
Situations for sustainable healthy nutrition	Residents/Staff	Photos	Mobile phone	Digital image data	.jpeg	.tif/.pdf	Paint Windows 10	Drive P:/OPINION Lab_CM 300	1 GB
Experiences with sustainable healthy nutrition		Interviews	Interview guideline	Audio	.mp3/.wav	.docx/.mx20	Word 2016/Maxqda		1 GB
Readiness for sustainable healthy nutrition		Questionnaire	Readiness of consumers to adopt an environmentally sustainable diet	Numbers	.sav	.sav	SPSS		1 GB

II Documentation and Metadata		
II.1	Metadata standards	We plan to use for the questionnaire age and sex as well as the qualification of the staff according to legal rules (GuKG; Art 15a B-VG).
II.2	Documentation of data	We plan to involve in the whole project about 10 residents and nursing home staff from one nursing home. Due to the fact, that only one nursing home participates during the whole project, we cannot guarantee that the data are anonymized in a way, that the personal of the rights and freedoms of data subjects are assured. This leads us to the decision not to publish our data.
II.3	Data quality control	In order to ensure the integrity and quality of the research data and increase the potential for data sharing, at least two project members will check randomly assigned 10% of the collected data. Moreover, interviewed participants, who agreed to check the audio file with the transcription will be contacted for member checking.

III Data Availability and Storage		
III.1	Data sharing strategy	Regarding data sharing during the research project: Off-campus access for the employees of the Medical University of Graz is via the Citrix portal or the Nextcloud of the Medical University of Graz. Any sensitive data that needs to be transmitted electronically will be transmitted pseudonymized by using the ACOnet file sender of the Medical University of Graz.
III.2	Data storage strategy	The research data underlying the publication, but also other relevant milestone versions of the project files are archived for at least ten years. During the project we will make use of network drive-P [Project] and the Medical University of Graz Nextcloud for storage and sharing of our research data – both ensuring automatic daily back-up. The expected total size of the remaining data is about 10 GB. The project results and all relevant research data will be stored for at least ten years at servers of Medical University of Graz using the backup service of the university, with no additional costs. No technical barriers. The data management plan will be reviewed at each annual meeting during the life of the project to ensure the success of our long-term data handling strategy.

IV		Legal and Ethical Aspects
IV.1	Legal aspects	<p>There are no legal barriers in making the research data accessible. However, due to the fact that the personal data in our project cannot be anonymized, our data cannot be made publically available.</p> <p>Medical University of Graz is entitled to exercise the unrestricted right to use data generated on behalf of or in the interest of Medical University of Graz. The authors or inventors retain the legally reserved right to be named, the right of university staff to independently publish scientific work and the right to be named as a (co-)author in the publication of research results.</p> <p>Articles are published as open access and therefore visible to all researchers and the public.</p>
IV.2	Ethical aspects	<p>Once a participant has given his/her informed consent to participation and data collection, the investigator will assign the participants a unique patient identification code. Therefore, data will be recorded in pseudonymized form using exclusively participants' identification code. The participants' identification code list will remain separated from the participants' datasets (P:\wv_sunrise). The study has been approved by the ethical committee of Medical University of Graz, (Number: 36-223 ex 23_24: Sunrise) and written informed consent will be obtained from all study participants.</p>